

Recycling Carbon Fibre Composites under Reduced Oxygen Concentrations: the Effect on Kinetics

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SUMMARY

Thermo-gravimetric analysis was carried out on carbon fibre composite material under reduced oxygen conditions. The results showed that reduced oxygen levels had a significant effect on rate of the devolatilisation of the polymer but played a more important role in slowing down the char oxidation. Kinetic modeling has been undertaken and good agreement has been found with the experimental results for the full range of oxygen concentration and heating rates investigated. The model can be used to investigate the operation of carbon fibre recycling processes.

Keywords: Carbon fibre / Recycling / TGA / degradation / oxygen concentration

INTRODUCTION

The market for Carbon Fibre Reinforcement Plastic (CFRP) is expected to increase by 37% by 2010. This increase is being driven mainly by the aircraft industry and renewable energy industry, where carbon fibre is being used in large quantities for large wind turbine blades.[1] As a consequence of the increase in CRFP utilization; an increasing quantity of waste CFRP is being created from manufacturing operations due to scrap components and the off-cuts created during part manufacture.[2] The need to recycle the scrap created during manufacture and components made from CFRP at the end of their life is widely accepted as an important issue. Whilst landfill or incineration are options for disposal, carbon fibre is a valuable material and recycling is potentially cost effective as well as being able to reduce the environmental impact.

There are a number of different processes that have been considered to reclaim carbon fibre from the end of life composites. Cunliffe and Williams[3] have studied a pyrolysis process and claim that pyrolysis can totally remove organic material from Sheet Molding Compound (SMC). However, there was some residual char remaining on the recovered

glass fibres. The char originated from the decomposition of the polymer matrix; although, it could be removed by mechanical action. More recently, sub- and supercritical fluid techniques have been shown to give good potential to recover both carbon fibre and glass fibre from composites. These techniques are broadly variations on two main techniques: pyrolysis and de-polymerisation by the chemical solvent.[4, 5]

In the fluidized bed recycling process developed at the University of Nottingham, recycled carbon fibre is produced by the degradation of CFRP in air in a heated fluidized bed. Understanding the kinetics of the process is important not only to understand the rate at which the material can be processed but also to understand the effect of temperature on the recycled carbon fibre.[2] Degradation kinetics for CFRP have generally been investigated in either air or an inert gas[6, 7] and there is little documentation of the effect of varying oxygen concentration on the degradation process.[8] The aim of this study is to investigate the effect of reduced oxygen levels on the thermal degradation kinetics of CFRP. In this paper, the thermal degradation kinetics of CFRP at the different heating rates and different oxygen levels will be studied experimentally and the kinetics will then be analyzed according to the Friedman method.[9] The result will be useful not only for understanding the thermal degradation process but also for development of thermal degradation models for the design of a fluidized bed reactor that can operate at the different oxygen conditions. The modeling can also be applied to other thermal processes in which CFRP is treated in reduced oxygen conditions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The investigations were carried out on a cured CFRP prepreg, MTM28/T600s, supplied by Advanced Composites Group. This composite system comprises T600s carbon fibres and MTM28 resin in which the fibre volume fraction is 62%. The MTM28.2 resin is based on Epichlorhydrin-bisphenol A resin.

Non-isothermal degradation of the prepreg was carried out by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA-TA instrument SDT-Q600). Samples of prepreg of approximately 10 mg were heated in the TGA under a mixture of air and nitrogen with oxygen concentrations ranging from 0% to 21% O₂ by volume from 30°C to 1000°C. Heating rates of 5, 10, 20 and 30K/min were used. The weight loss with temperature was recorded every second and evaluated by using TA Universal analytical software. The data were analyzed by Friedman's method to determine the kinetics of the process and to evaluate the pre-exponential factor (A), activation energy (E_a) and reaction order (n) [9].

Analytical parameters from TGA data

The thermal degradation of CFRP is a complex problem in the area of composite recycling area as it requires understanding of both the reaction mechanisms and degradation kinetics. In particular, degradation of the polymer matrix in CFRP is complex as there are

many different degradation reactions. However, in this study, the preliminary kinetic parameters are evaluated using the following simplified reactions.

It is widely accepted that the rate change of residual mass (α) with time (t) can be written as a function of the residual concentration in the form.

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k \cdot f(\alpha) \quad (2)$$

Where, kinetic rate, (k) is expressed in the Arrhenius form:

$$k = A \cdot \exp\left(\frac{-E}{R \cdot T}\right) \quad (3)$$

where, A is a pre-exponential value, R is a gas constant (8314 kJ/(kmol K)), E is an activation energy, (kJ/kg) and T is temperature (K). Thus

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = A \cdot \exp\left(\frac{-E}{R \cdot T}\right) \cdot (1-\alpha)^n \quad (4)$$

For a given heating rate (β) K/s

$$\beta \frac{d\alpha}{dT} = A \cdot \exp\left(\frac{-E}{R \cdot T}\right) \cdot (1-\alpha)^n \quad (5)$$

The Friedman method[9] is one of the most popular models for evaluating the kinetic parameters of polymer reactions. In this technique the kinetic curves are plotted at the different heating rates and this gives rise to the Friedman method being known as the multi-curve model. The activation energy can be obtained by plotting $\ln\left(\beta \frac{d\alpha}{dT}\right)$ against $(1/T)$. Based on the assumption that the conversion factor is a function of temperature and is independent of heating rate, it is thus possible to get a straight line from which E (activation energy) can be obtained from the slope, as shown in equation (6):

$$\ln\left(\beta \frac{d\alpha}{dT}\right) = \left(\frac{-E}{R \cdot T}\right) + \ln A + n \ln(1-\alpha) \quad (6)$$

In order to get the pre-exponential constant (A) and the reaction order (n), equation (6) is rearranged by moving $\left(\frac{-E}{R \cdot T}\right)$ to the left hand side and substituting the activation energy obtained from equation (6) back in equation (7). Equation (7) is in a linear form which has reaction order as slope. The pre-exponential factor can be obtained from the intercept.

$$\ln\left(\beta \frac{d\alpha}{dT}\right) + \left(\frac{-E}{R \cdot T}\right) = n \ln(1-\alpha) + \ln A \quad (7)$$

If the kinetic model is written in ODE form as an initial value problem, it can be solved by using the Rung-Kutta method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Thermal degradation kinetics of CRFP under a Pyrolysis process

Figure 1a shows TG-curves and DTG-curves at different oxygen levels for a 10K/min heating rate. Figure 1b shows the effect of different heating rates. It can be seen that the oxygen concentration has an influence on the polymer decomposition. In the absence of oxygen, thermal degradation (pyrolysis) takes place in a single stage at approximate 275-475°C and no further degradation takes place at higher temperature. It is likely that most of the heat energy is utilized for breaking the cross-linking in the molecule structure of the epoxy resin. This gives a mass loss of about 29-31% after which most of the organic matter has been volatilized leaving a residual char on the carbon fire surface. It is impossible to remove this char in a pyrolysis environment (zero oxygen); however, it can easily be removed by introducing oxygen.

Thermal degradation kinetics of CRFP under different oxygen concentrations

Thermal degradation in the presence of oxygen concentrations from 6% to 21% initially takes place in two degradation stages between about 270-376°C and 376-475°C.

Figure 1. TG and DTG curves for Prepreg MTM28.2/T600s under different oxygen levels
 (a) the effect of difference oxygen content: (0-21% O₂ content) at 10 K/min
 (b) the effect of difference heating rates (5-30 K/min) at 6% O₂ content

These are the initial degradation stage and the main pyrolysis stage (Figure 1a.). Unlike the pyrolysis process, there are two noticeable changes in volatilization and it should be noted that, in terms of peak and final temperature, the second degradation stage is exactly the same as the degradation stage under the nitrogen gas (pyrolysis). Jing[5] seems to support this view and points out that the initial phase of polymer degradation needs oxygen to react with the polymer to release water, volatile organic compounds and radical groups. The main polymer degradation is an anaerobic reaction. As this degradation mechanism is the same, either under air or nitrogen, it would be called a pyrolysis stage. At 475-650°C there is a further reaction that is understood to be the oxidation of char formed during the second degradation. Finally, above 600°C there is progressive oxidation of the carbon fibre. It can be seen that the concentration of oxygen influences somewhat the initial rate of degradation of the polymer and also to a greater extent the rate of oxidation of the char. Both of these effects are important influences on the processing of CFRP in a fluidized bed.

Effect of heating rate and oxygen level

Table 1 lists the degradation reaction characteristics in term of the final reaction temperature of the CFRP at various oxygen levels. Figure 1a shows that the oxygen levels do not affect the T_{peak} in pyrolysis period, while the heating rates shift these peak temperatures (Figure 1b). In particular, the height and area under the DTG are a function of reaction rate and the loss of mass. Although, the heating rate affects the maximum reaction temperatures at the same oxygen levels, the oxygen concentrations do not affect the maximum reaction temperature in the pyrolysis phase at the same heating rates.

Table 1. Reaction characteristic of CFRP under the various oxygen levels

Carrier Gas	β (K/min)	T_1^* (K)	T_2 (K)	T_3 (K)	T_4 (K)
21% O ₂	5	606	707	812	1048
	10	649	740	882	1121
	20	661	754	907	1175
	30	668	760	922	1216
18% O ₂	5	629	715	858	1077
	10	646	738	887	1133
	20	659	751	914	1193
	30	674	759	922	1220
12% O ₂	5	638	720	870	1096
	10	654	736	912	1171
	20	665	743	917	1217
	30	670	763	944	1292
6% O ₂	5	637	724	884	1145
	10	656	739	931	1232
	20	670	756	945	1298
	30	672	764	965	1303

Note : T_n is the end of reaction temperature at the different oxygen level.

T_1 is at the end of the initial degradation stage

T_2 is at the end of the pyrolysis stage

T_3 is at the end of the char oxidation stage

T_4 is at the end of the carbon fibre oxidation stage

In Table 1 it can be seen that the end of reaction temperatures were generally increased at higher heating rates and the same oxygen concentrations. However, it may be noted that the temperature difference between T_2 and T_1 tends to be constant. The next section discusses more about the temperature difference between start and end of each degradation phase. Figure 2 shows the effect of heating rate on the degradation temperature in each stage. It seems that the heating rate has a significant effect on char and carbon fibre oxidation. However, for the pyrolysis stage the pyrolysis temperature (ΔT_{py}) tends towards a constant value for every heating rate while it gradually changes, by 5 K or less, for different oxygen concentrations. So, the pyrolysis temperature is independent of heating rate and oxygen concentration.

Although the ΔT seems to be constant for the pyrolysis stage, it was significantly different in both the char and carbon fibre oxidation stages. Moreover, the study suggests that the lower oxygen levels lead to higher temperature differences at the same heating rate.

Figure 2 The different temperatures between the different degradation stages. Oxygen content = 6% (Δ), 12% (\diamond) 18% (\circ) and 21% (\square)

Kinetics parameters.

Table 2 lists the degradation kinetics parameters obtained from Friedman method.[9] for each of the four stages in the degradation. It can be seen that the maximum activation energy was in the second stage of degradation. This is a non-oxygen reactive stage so it needed only heat energy to degrade cross-linking.

Table 2. Degradation kinetic parameters of CFRP under the various oxygen levels

Carrier Gas	Degradation stages	E (J/kg-K)	A (sec ⁻¹)	n [-]
21% O ₂	1	86 924.2	1.210× 10 ⁵	0.4547
	2	180 840.6	3.482× 10 ¹¹	0.9581
	3	122 732.8	4.236× 10 ⁵	0.9271
	4	83 762.0	1.799× 10 ¹	0.0068
18% O ₂	1	123 253.0	2.417× 10 ⁸	0.9992
	2	194 662.4	3.690× 10 ¹²	0.9562
	3	153 215.1	3.614× 10 ⁷	1.0710
	4	115 396.5	6.170× 10 ²	0.2421
12% O ₂	1	131 052.5	1.094× 10 ⁹	1.1895
	2	208 206.1	4.247× 10 ¹³	1.0703
	3	137 074.2	2.451× 10 ⁶	1.0642
	4	90 731.1	2.536× 10 ¹	0.0838
6% O ₂	1	132 138.8	1.113× 10 ⁹	1.1254
	2	192 586.9	2.633× 10 ¹²	0.9963
	3	134 380.8	1.068× 10 ⁶	1.1794
	4	103 564.8	6.613× 10 ¹	0.2558

The degradation kinetic parameters listed in Table 2 can be substituted into equation (4). Equations (8a) and (8b) are a set of degradation modeling equations for CFRP under 6% O₂ concentration.

$$\frac{d\alpha_i}{dT} = \left(\frac{A_i}{\beta}\right) \cdot \exp\left(\frac{-E_i}{R \cdot T}\right) \cdot (1-\alpha)^n \quad I = 1,2,3 \text{ and } 4 \quad (8a)$$

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dT} = \sum_{i=1}^4 W_i \frac{d\alpha_i}{dT} \quad (8b)$$

Where W_i is an individual phase mass ratio which is the ratio between the individual mass at the specific levels divided by the initial mass. For example, the W_i for 6%O₂ at different heating rate are listed in Table 3 and for 30 K/min at different O₂ concentrations in Table 4.

Table 3 individual phase mass ratio (W_i) for the 6%O₂ at the difference heating rates

degradation phase, i heating rate, β	1 (initial phase)	2 (Pyrolysis)	3 (char oxidize)	4 (CF oxidize)
5 K/min	0.09 89	0.10 84	0.14 79	0.64 34
10 K/min	0.09 34	0.12 03	0.13 62	0.64 42
20 K/min	0.10 59	0.09 85	0.11 16	0.67 90
30 K/min	0.09 06	0.10 76	0.09 86	0.69 50

Table 4 individual phase mass ratio (W_i) for the 30K/min at the difference Oxygen content

degradation phase, i	1	2	3	4
	(initial phase)	(Pyrolysis)	(char oxidize)	(CF oxidize)
heating rate, β				
6% O ₂	0.09 06	0.10 76	0.09 86	0.69 50
12% O ₂	0.09 23	0.12 87	0.11 27	0.65 80
18% O ₂	0.11 06	0.12 65	0.14 19	0.62 99
21% O ₂	0.10 18	0.14 37	0.13 64	0.60 98

Figure 3 shows the comparison between the computation results by Friedman method and experiment results for TGA for 6% O₂ and different heating rates and Figure 4 shows the comparison for a heating rate of 30K/min at different oxygen concentrations. It can be seen that in all cases there is a good fit between the Friedman method and the experimental data. In the fluidized bed CFRP recycling process, the carbon fibre separates from the polymer matrix by thermal energy. The result shows that limitation of oxygen content may not significant effect on the first and the second stages; however, it can shift the char oxidation temperature to higher level and this will affect the rate at which the fibres are separated from each other and released into the gas stream in the fluidised bed.

Figure 3 Comparison between TG curve and Friedman model (condition: 6% O₂ and 5 -30 K/min Heating rate)

Figure 4 Comparison between TG curve and Friedman model (condition: 30 K/min and 6% - 21% O₂)

CONCLUSION

Unlike, CFRP degradation under Pyrolysis conditions, the thermal degradation kinetics of CFRP in the presence of oxygen can lead to four different degradation stages these are the initial stage, the pyrolysis stage, the char oxidation stage and carbon fibre oxidation stage. It seems that the most degradation energy is used for degradation of the polymer matrix in the second phase. Regarding to the kinetics modeling, the experiment results agree well with empirical modeling using the Friedman method [9]. It is likely that the oxygen content limit does not affect the main polymer degradation (the pyrolysis stage); however, it has an influence on the char oxidation stage. In particular, the reduced rate at which char oxidation takes place will extend the residence time of the CFRP in the fluidised bed process and this will affect process throughput and may influence mechanical property degradation and hence the quality of the recycled product. The results are also of value to pyrolysis recycling processes and indicate the requirement for oxygen to oxidise the char produced to yield clean recycled fibres.

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